

ISic1489

Dedication to Hermes

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

found approx 200m north of Temple of Concord ('terreno Sclafani) in 1918

Coordinates

37.291514, 13.591975

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 1869

Physical Description

A square block of blue-grey marble with white veins. The block is intact on all sides, but appears to have been broken in half (with a further break in the upper part) at some point in the (modern) past, and repaired. There is minor damage to the top left, top middle and bottom right of the front face. The upper face contains a large square recess centred in relation to the block (30 cm wide x 34 cm front to back, border on left/right is 15 cm; border front/back is 14 cm), parallel to the overall form of the block.

Dimensions

Height 30 cm

Width 64 cm

Depth 57.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 18-25 mm

Line 2: 18-24 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 18-20 mm

Text

1. Φάλακρος : Θεωδώρου

2. Ἑρμᾶι : ἀνέθηκε

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

Phalakros son of Theodoros dedicated (this statue) to Hermes

Translation (it)

Phalacros, figlio di Theodoros, ad Hermes dedicò

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644995

EDR 136102

PHI 329602

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0035

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 183 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 421

Langlotz, E. 1943. Die Ephebenstatue in Agrigent. *Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts, Römische Abteilung*. 58: 204-212. At abb.3

De Waele, J. 1971. Acragas Graeca: die historische Topographie des griechischen Akragas auf Sizilien. 1, Historischer Teil. *Archeologische studiën van het Nederlands Instituut te Rome*. 's-Gravenhage. At 32-33 no.3 pl.4

Griffo, P. 1987. Il museo archeologico regionale di Agrigento. Rome. At 188 fig.163

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1489. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354175>

Photo J. Prag, courtesy Agrigento Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo